

BEUCITIZEN
BARRIERS TOWARDS EU CITIZENSHIP

Dissemination plan for bEUcitizen and a report of year 1

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this document we describe the dissemination strategy for the bEUcitizen project. The plan is designed to maximize the potential impact of the project through the implementation of broadly-based and efficiently targeted dissemination activities for the findings of the project. To this end, three main target groups have been identified:

1. The Academic Community
2. Policy Makers
3. Young Europeans

In order to maximize the potential impact on these target groups, specific dissemination activities and ambitions have been developed for each target group specifically.

The overall objectives of the plan are to maximize internal and external communications, to publish results in the academic field and in non-specialist language, to inform and train policy makers and young Europeans in such a way that they will transfer the aims and knowledge of the bEUcitizen project.

1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of the 'bEUcitizen' project is to identify, through a historical and contemporary study of models of citizenship, workable solutions to some of the challenges currently faced by the EU in its attempt to further develop EU citizenship. The project is based on the assumption that citizenship should not be understood as merely a legal or constitutional category, with a homogeneous character created by that legal framework, but as a category of interdependent rules and practices. Citizenship is thus perceived as a multi-layered phenomenon, which is reflected by the approach of the 'bEUcitizen' Consortium, focusing on the multi-layered and multidimensional character of European citizenship, its multitudinous effects on different categories of citizens and the existence of a multiplicity of barriers to the exercising of rights. Focusing on the interaction between rules and practices, and on 'multiple multiples', the 'bEUcitizen' Consortium firmly believes that its research will contribute to filling systematic gaps in current research on EU citizenship and will also lead to innovative scenarios for the development of citizenship within the EU.

This research programme aims to present the EU project as a space for democracy, the rule of law and fundamental rights, with EU citizenship as a core value. It will do so by identifying and investigating the multitude of barriers that exist to achieving a common conception of EU citizenship and in getting citizens to exercise the rights connected to the various social and legal contexts and conditions to EU citizenship. One of its key contributions is to address the fundamental problem that the EU is trying to reverse the historical sequence. In earlier historical phases - the medieval city and later the nation state - there was first a social identity, based on locality, shared language and culture, to which rights were subsequently attached. The European Union is now trying to do the opposite: providing rights, in the expectation that a shared identity will develop out of them. The bEUcitizen project seeks to overcome this conundrum by highlighting models of citizenship that are at one and the same time multidimensional and multi-layered.

This document strongly builds on deliverable *12.1 Dissemination plan* and aims to provide a more concrete overview of the type of activities that are being planned and how they should eventually contribute to the overall intended impacts of the project. It should be read as a further elaboration and practical development of the original dissemination plan. These intended impacts were identified in the original project proposal for the bEUcitizen project: *1) A boost in academic research on EU citizenship, 2) Policy development, implementation and evaluation to encourage citizenship and remove barriers, and 3) Civil realisation of EU citizenship rights and responsibilities.*

In order to focus our dissemination efforts and enhance the chances of achieving the intended impact, three target groups have been identified, corresponding to the three points of intended impact: *1) Academic community, 2) Policy makers and 3) Young Europeans under the age of 35 (Young Europeans).* These three groups can further be split into different subgroups, which will be done in Chapter 2, in order to stronger connect to each target group.

This document is structured as follows: chapter 2 contains a more elaborate overview of our target groups and the rationale behind them. Chapter 3 focuses on the conference and event coverage. Chapter 4 provides an overview of the communication tools that have been developed to maximize the visibility of the project. Finally, chapter 5 reports the dissemination activities the coordination team and individual researchers from the bEUcitizen consortium engaged in during the first year of the project (month 1 – 12).

2 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The bEUcitizen dissemination strategy focusses on three specific groups in order to achieve its intended impacts. These groups are: the Academic Community, Policy Makers and Young Europeans.

2.1 THE ACADEMIC COMMUNITY

The contribution that the bEUcitizen project aims to make to the Academic Community, which will boost academic research is threefold:

1. *Contribution to (conceptual) understanding of citizenship:* because of the consortium’s interdisciplinary character, more comprehensive theoretical models and analyses regarding European citizenship can be carried out. Case studies accompany these theoretical models, resulting in a more comprehensive understanding of the concept of citizenship in the different research fields.
2. *Methodological impact:* the multidisciplinary and multidimensional approach of the bEUcitizen project should raise mutual multidisciplinary understanding of the multidimensional character of citizenship. To facilitate this understanding, linguistic and conceptual principles will be formulated, exchanged and shared within the project. This ensures a clear methodological description and explanation on any external form of communication on the project’s research efforts, facilitating mutual understanding in the wider academic community.
3. *Boost research on the interplay of rules and practices:* by combining empirical and normative methodologies, research on the interplay between rules and practices will be furthered.

Reaching out to the academic community will happen by means of (scientific) publications and through networks, platforms and events. Furthermore, training activities will be organized for young researchers.

2.1.1 Publications

1. *Open Access:* All public bEUcitizen publications that are classified as Working Papers or research reports are published as Open Access publications¹. To ensure that the project remains identifiable, Open Access publication of the Working Papers has been organised as follows:

Open Access	Description	Online address
bEUcitizen website	A separate ‘Publications’ section on the website has been established. It has an easy search function where papers can be found by Work Package, researcher or key words. All the public deliverables of the project can be found and downloaded from the website, as well as related materials that are provided by the consortium’s researchers.	www.beucitizen.eu/publications
ZENODO	Online Open Access database, specifically targeted at European projects. The OpenAIRE database sources from ZENODO, as well as online search engines such as for instance Google Scholar , ensuring a wide availability of the bEUcitizen papers and reports.	The bEUcitizen collection: http://zenodo.org/collection/user-beucitizen

¹ Publications that are to be submitted to (peer reviewed) journals are excluded.

2. *Academic journals:* Publications that are intended for submission to a (peer reviewed) journal, will not be published online on the bEUcitizen website or in the ZENODO database. These papers will be submitted to high impact journals to ensure maximum impact from the scientific work that is carried out. Journals targeted for paper publications will include the ones in which our researchers have previously been published. These journals include for instance:

AB Jurisprudentie Bestuursrechtspraak	Low Countries Historical Review
Administration & Society	Nederlands Tijdschrift voor Europees Recht (NTER)
Centre for Study of European Labour Law "Massimo D'Antona"	Population Review
Common Market Law Review	Public Administration
Constellations	Regulation & Governance
European Gender Equality Law Review	Revista d'estudis autonòmics i federals
European Law Review	Revista General de Derecho Administrativo
Journal of Contemporary European Research	Revista jurídica de Castilla y León
Journal of European Public Policy	Scandinavian Economic History Review
Journal of European Social Policy	SEW, Tijdschrift voor Europees en Economisch Recht
Journal of Family Issues	Social Politics
Journal of Social Policy	The German Law Journal
L'Observatoire de la société britannique	Utrecht Law Review
Law & Policy	Zeitschrift für Politische Theorie

3. *Book series:* The bEUcitizen project will publish a book series existing of 10 editions at the end of the projects' time. It is intended that the books are being published by the same publishing house and will be identifiable as a unique series. Possible publishing houses, where many of our researchers have published books before, have been listed and contacted. These include: Ashgate publishers, Palgrave, Oxford University Press, Springer, Edgar Elgar and Policy Press. During the course of the project's second year, the final choice for a series and publishing house will be made.

2.1.2 Networks and platforms

Knowledge dissemination and exchange of the bEUcitizen project will furthermore take place through the vast number of different (inter)disciplinary professional associations our consortium researchers are involved in. These interactive networks and forums include for instance:

- European Consortium of Political Research
- The European Social Policy Network
- The European Sociological Association
- Council of European Studies (United States)
- The Economic History Society
- European social science history association
- ESPANET
- FIDE conferences
- Law and Society
- National and European associations of European law, including migration law associations
- Fundamental Rights Agencies

By targeting the Academic Community through publications, participating in various networks and platforms, hosting and attending seminars, workshops and other events, we are able to reach out to a wide public and exchange knowledge with a wide range of academic disciplines. At the same time valuable feedback can be received as well as insights and input for the project, and the bEUcitizen research can be disseminated and its impact on EU citizenship can be maximized by boosting academic research.

2.1.3 Other EU funded projects

A number of projects that have been funded by the EU have been identified for possible collaboration. We are aiming to get these collaborations and shared sessions for information exchange running by invitation from the European Commission’s officers. That way, chances to having successful meetings increase and collaborations will be more likely.

Interesting projects that have been identified by the bEUcitizen project include:

Project acronym	Project title	Website
STYLE	Strategic Transitions for Youth Labour in Europe	http://www.style-research.eu/
LIVEWHAT	Living With Hard Times - Citizen’s resilience in times of crisis	http://www.livewhat.unige.ch/
FRAME	Fostering Human Rights Among European (External and Internal) Policies	http://www.fp7-frame.eu/

2.1.4 Training of young researchers and academic professionals

Within the Academic Community a subgroup can be identified: young researchers. In order to guarantee a lasting impact, bEUcitizen aims to pool expertise for training in the area of European citizenship. Different trainings are offered in different settings:

- Many professors in the bEUcitizen consortium are supervising PhD students that work on topics of the bEUcitizen project.
- The bi-annual course in Dubrovnik (Croatia) for Master of Science students from all over Europe and Turkey is an example of how bEUcitizen contributes to the training of the next generation of researchers (www.inclusionexclusion.eu).
- BEUcitizen researchers are furthermore involved in the ESPANET summer schools for PhD students that are organised yearly in rotating host countries.
- At the bEUcitizen mid-term and final conferences, PhD students are specifically encouraged to participate and submit papers for the panel discussions.

2.2 POLICY MAKERS

The bEUcitizen project sets out to actively affect *policy development, implementation and evaluation to encourage citizenship and remove barriers*. To this end, policy makers are an important focus group for the projects’ dissemination activities.

To allow for a focussed approach where relevant information is shared with the target audience, policy makers are differentiated into the following groups:

1. *National Policy Makers in the Member States*: these policy makers face questions relating to citizenship on a different level than European Policy Makers. Often they deal on a daily basis with practical problems

related to the exercise of rights and responsibilities of European citizens. National Policy Makers will be invited to national events organised by the bEUcitizen consortium partners, to inform them about the project, its outcome and to discuss particular national challenges those policy makers face. Through these interactive national events, the project helps to evaluate existing policies, contributes to further development and improvement of national policies in various fields of (European) citizenship and the implementation thereof.

2. *European Policy Makers*: these are for example (but not exclusively) the European Commission (in particular DG Internal Market and Services, DG Education, DG Employment, DG Justice, DG Competition and DG Research) and the European Parliament. These policy makers will be invited to the bEUcitizen mid-term and final conferences, where they will engage in interactive sessions to discuss the barriers and tensions of European citizenship.

2.2.1 Specific Output

1. *Policy briefs* will be produced by the project to communicate research results. These will consist of short presentations in written form, six to ten pages long, with key and catchy information that definitely attract the highest attention from policymaking and policy decision circles. Policy relevant results will be published when appropriate throughout the project in a series of policy briefs in which researchers can articulate their evidence-based conclusions in the form of constructive policy recommendations.
2. *Impact assessment tool* will be developed to help Policy Makers evaluate ex ante the impact of new policies on the consequences for possible barriers in exercising citizenship rights.
3. *Report with scenarios for 2030* based on our research, in which researchers from all work packages will establish scenarios for the medium-term development of the concept of EU citizenship in daily life.
4. *Newsletter articles*: researchers are invited to write articles for our six-monthly Newsletter that are interesting for Policy Makers to read.

2.3 YOUNG EUROPEANS

An important, if not crucial, aspect of the project will be to identify ways in which European citizens become aware of and can be encouraged to exercise their rights. One of the aims explicitly identified by the bEUcitizen project is that its output should lead to “civil realization of EU citizenship rights and responsibilities”, which could ultimately contribute to the further development of EU citizenship. To make a lasting impact on the experience and exercise of European citizenship, it is particularly important to reach young people in Europe. Those young Europeans who are still in school or who have just started their careers and/or families, and are *under the age of thirty-five*.

In particular, three sub-groups can be identified: 1) primary school students; 2) high school students; 3) young European adults under 35. Out of these subgroups our specific focus is on groups two and three. In order to reach these subgroups, we are aiming to employ a number of specific activities:

1. Cooperation with third parties is being sought to develop *a documentary* on the barriers and tensions European citizens and entrepreneurs face. This documentary is aimed at the wider public and should particularly be interesting to young Europeans. It further expands the creative use of (new) media by the bEUcitizen project.
2. Side-events and specific sessions are foreseen at events and conferences organised by members of the bEUcitizen consortium. During these sessions, issues surrounding European citizenship will be

discussed that are of specific interest to our target subgroups. To these events, the following stakeholders will be invited:

- Sector organisations in education - invited to bEUcitizen conferences and seminars
 - Young European associations (EU) level contacted and invited to our events
 - National associations of high-school students (like the Dutch LAKS) shall be contacted by the consortium's partners
3. Researchers from the bEUcitizen consortium will make an effort to visit and lecture at high-schools. Contributing to the awareness amongst young Europeans of the rights, tensions and barriers that are connected to European citizenship.

One Work Package in the bEUcitizen project is specifically designed to target this group of young Europeans: WP11 - Forward Looking Activities.

2.3.1 Specific output

Teaching packages (14-16 year old teenagers) are being developed that focus on European Citizenship.

3 CONFERENCE AND EVENT COVERAGE

The most important channel for engaging with the Academic Community and Policy Makers is to organize, attend and present at high-level conferences and events.

Through participation at conferences, bEUcitizen members exchange their views with other scholars and professionals. By providing presentations at these conferences and by publishing in various disciplinary and highly regarded academic journals we will be reaching out beyond the narrow academic communities focused on citizenship and will also connect to related academic communities globally. The effectiveness of our academic dissemination will be measured by whether and, the extent to which, EU citizenship becomes a core concept of analysis in the respective academic communities. Furthermore, if we present our work at the annual conferences of the Council of European Studies in the United States, we are able to effectively target the European Studies community in North America and most likely have an impact on the teaching curriculum at the respective universities.

Until now, a number of contributions have already been made (see Table 1, Report). As the presentations reported were made during the project first year, their aim was primarily to introduce bEUcitizen to the Academic Community. With the first results available, conferences and seminars have become the main ground to discuss findings, to collect suggestions and to exchange knowledge.

On the website there is a list, constantly updated, of appropriate external conferences, workshops, etc., which consortium partners visit in order to present the project's outputs and/or in which special sessions could be organised.

Conferences and National events are very important opportunities for involving National and European Policy Makers. In this respect, each partner in the bEUcitizen consortium will organize a national seminar or event to which National Policy Makers are invited. During these seminars / events, current national issues regarding European citizenship will be discussed as well as long-term visions and outcomes from the bEUcitizen project.

These national events are not necessarily required to be high-profile (although they might be), they are specifically designed to discuss the barriers towards European citizenship on the national level. Events that are currently being planned already are:

Country	City	Topic ²	Invitations are sent to	Organised by	Event date
Hungary	Budapest	bEUcitizen stakeholders event on civil rights		CEUR	1 December 2014
Spain	Barcelona	Secession of Catalonia: what would be the consequences?	Politicians from national and regional level; Scientists; Civil Society Organisations; Youth Organisations; Press	UPF	May 2015
Spain	Barcelona		All audiences, including students, scholars, policymakers, civil society and other stakeholders	UPF, UZH	May 2015
UK	London		Policy Makers; Civil Society Organisations; EU Commission representation in London	UOXF	Summer 2015

² Topics are preliminary and should be considered working titles.

Apart from these National events, Work Package coordinators will organise small events as well during the course of the project. These will mostly take place near the end of the project. For these events, where appropriate, policy makers and young Europeans (also through national and European associations) will be invited as well.

The bEUcitizen midterm and final conferences will become landmarks of the project. Findings of the bEUcitizen research project shall be presented for an international and interdisciplinary public. Scholars from outside the project are invited to these conferences and to submit their paper for panel discussions and paper presentations. An exchange of knowledge will be accomplished by this interactive, two-day event organised by the bEUcitizen consortium. Furthermore, policy makers from Brussels in particular are invited to participate in the different forum discussions as well as a number of planned interactive side events (such as a special session on 'Youth, Education and Employment' that is planned for the mid-term conference in Zagreb). Especially policy makers from DG Education and Culture; DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion; DG Justice and DG Research and Innovation are invited to both conferences.

	Conference title³	Dates open conference	Location
Mid-term conference	Being a Citizen of Europe	29-30 June 2015	Zagreb, Croatia
Final conference	CITIZENSHIP IN THE EUROPEAN UNION Barriers and tensions - the way forward	April 2017	Brussels, Belgium

³ Conference titles are preliminary

4 COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Beyond the abovementioned specific instruments for the relevant target groups, a broad array of dissemination channels have been conceived and will be used to boost the visibility of the project.

This chapter gives an overview of the communication tools (project website, templates, logo, flyers, newsletter) that have been developed to maximize the impact of the project, to disseminate its findings and to facilitate the internal and external exchange of information.

4.1 PROJECT WEBSITE

The bEUcitizen project website (<http://www.beucitizen.eu/>) constitutes a web-based dissemination tool that provides general information about the project itself (topic, goals and structure) and the people involved. It serves in particular as a source of information for the general public interested in the project results, activities and events.

The website contains four pages that are constantly updated (other pages are more static in nature and do not need to be updated regularly):

4. *news*: where documents published by the European Institutions, news or other information of interest both for our researcher and for the public interested in the topic are made available;
5. *blog*: weekly updated with contributions written by researchers;
6. *agenda*: with upcoming events organized within the Consortium or by third-parties;
7. *publications*: where all the project deliverable and other publications are uploaded or announced.

Figure 1 (Annex) shows a screenshot of the home page of the website.

Visitors are given the possibility to leave comments through a moderated communication interface. Statistics about the webpage visitors are collected using Google Analytics (Figure 2, Annex)

4.2 TEAM SITE (GOOGLE ACCOUNT)

To facilitate the sharing of documents among the project members an intranet has been set up using Google Drive. On this drive important documents, guidelines and information are being shared by the coordination team with the project members. As well, Work Package teams store presentations, draft deliverables and reports, datasets and other work in progress to be shared within their Work Packages on this drive.

As a result, the latest version of each document is always easily accessible and there is no need for sending back and forth draft versions of the research. This is an important tool in preventing confusion with researchers, both for the Coordination Team as well as within the Work Packages. The user friendliness of the Google Drive system results in a high usage of this intranet page for bEUcitizen.

4.3 SOCIAL NETWORKS

BEUcitizen makes also use of social networks, as Twitter and Facebook (Figure 3, Annex). These more recent communication channels enable to reach and to interact with the widest audience possible and to keep a fast-moving flow of project news.

The distribution of messages and their reception through the virtual community are shown by the number of likes, sharing and comments on Facebook or by the number of followers, citations and Retweets on Twitter.

Furthermore, an insights tool developed by Facebook allow us to monitor, among the others, the post reach and the number of viewers (Figure 4, Annex).

4.4 NEWSLETTER

A bEUcitizen newsletter is sent out every 6 months, in July and December. The newsletter will present key results achieved and activities carried out as well as upcoming events of interests.

The newsletter will be distributed to our mailing list of parties interested in the project and can be easily forwarded to others by recipients.

Third parties interested in our newsletter can easily subscribe from the form on the project website.

4.5 CORPORATE IDENTITY

An integral part of our dissemination strategy is our corporate identity. All communication from and within the project will have the same, uniform lay-out, use of logo's and colours. The logos developed for the project reflect the many aspects which reflect the many 'multiples' of our project:

	<p>The elements of whole logo of our project symbolize:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · the different colours and different directions of the triangles: our multidisciplinary · the gridlines: the borders around and within the EU across which its citizens (are supposed to) move · the three colours of triangles: our three clusters that fit well together to form the large triangle: our integrated multidisciplinary research project
	<p>The logo for Cluster I: The Multi-layered Character of Citizenship: Variations across Space and Time</p> <p>This cluster is visualised by the vertical hour-glass in lighter blue in the middle of the logo, indicating both the passage of time, and concentric layers of identities</p>
	<p>The logo for Cluster II: Multidimensional Rights of Citizenship</p> <p>This cluster is visualised by the horizontal scales in green, referring to the ideal of a balance between different rights</p>
	<p>The logo for Cluster III: Multitudinous Effects of Rights on Multiple Categories of Citizens</p> <p>This cluster is visualised by the solidly standing orange triangles, but located at some distance from each other, in the corners, representing different categories of citizens</p>

Templates for the deliverables and letters as well as a PowerPoint template including the logo have been designed. In particular the Power Point template can be used to develop slides for bEUcitizen presentations during conferences and seminars.

4.6 PRINTED TOOLS

Flyers with clear and attractive presentations of the project, its objectives and its partners will be of valuable use in the early stages of the project, taking the function of a business card of the consortium which can be used in professional contacts. Brochures produced at the project's outset and during its finalisation phase will serve to physically disseminate the project's intentions and results.

4.7 OTHER COMMUNICATION TOOLS

We are actively looking into the possibilities to work together with artists in order to engage in beyond the state of the art dissemination of the project's findings, in particular where tensions between various citizens' rights are concerned. The cooperation we are looking for does not only make our research more accessible for the (Young) European citizen; it should also help Policy Makers in their understanding of the different tensions and barriers that are still persistent in the European citizenship.

At the moment, we are in contact with *Pink Pony Express* and *Circus Europe* to see if we can work together on (a) dissemination activit(y)(ies).

	Possibilities for cooperation	Preferred timing	Website
Circus Europe	Searching for possibilities of an exhibition of their work during the bEUcitizen final conference; other possibilities include the development of a booklet where bEUcitizen findings and different art forms (poetry, imagery) meet.	Specifically aimed at the mid-term and final conference.	http://circus-europe.blogspot.nl/
Pink Pony Express	For example looking into the possibility of creating a documentary film about real life tensions and barriers that European citizens and entrepreneurs face.	Throughout the project's lifetime - final dissemination products finished at the end of the project: April 2015	http://www.pinkponyexpress.nl/

Furthermore, we are currently planning to organize a press conference during the mid-term and final conferences. Traditional media such as newspapers and radio are important for the bEUcitizen project to involve. Journalists from these traditional media are therefore invited to each of the public dissemination events organised by bEUcitizen, including mid-term/final conferences and national events. Furthermore, bEUcitizen researchers have been explicitly instructed to mention the bEUcitizen project when they are interviewed on related topics by traditional media.

4.8 OVERVIEW OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES USED PER TARGET GROUPS

The various dissemination tools will be utilised in specific and distinguished ways to communicate information about the project and the scientific and policy-relevant results of bEUcitizen to the key target groups in the most effective manner possible.

The table below shows the dissemination focus of bEUcitizen and it gives a brief impression of the relevancy of each activity per target group.

X = very relevant to target group

XX = very strong relevance to and focused on target group

		Target group		
		Academic Community	Policy Makers	Young Europeans
Tools	Online Activities	XX	XX	XX
	Printed Tools	X	XX	X
	Policy briefs	X	XX	
	Networking the networks	XX	X	
	Publications	XX	X	
	Conferences coverage	XX	XX	X
	Media instruments		XX	XX

5 DISSEMINATION REPORT - YEAR 1

The dissemination report describes the activities that took place during the first year of the project and which ensured visibility of bEUcitizen.

5.1 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

All our researchers have been asked to keep track of the activities undertaken that represented a mean to circulate our project and to create awareness about it. The project, however, is only in its first stage and many of our researchers have just started to develop their first deliverables. Most of the dissemination activities therefore focus on the results of the first deliverables submitted; on topics that are going to be studied in upcoming deliverables; on issues linked to the main themes of the project.

The table below (table 1) gives an overview of the main, very successful dissemination activities performed during the first year of the project. These activities aimed at promoting the project, both through the direct dissemination of research results and through referring to bEUcitizen during other events. Our researchers took part in different conferences, addressing a public of experts. But they also lectured to students and school children. Some researchers have published in scientific journals, referring directly to bEUcitizen.

The table is structured as follows: details of the consortium member, researcher who carried out the activity, description of the activity, further information about the activity itself; target group⁴. Furthermore, all the listed activities are accompanied by evidences, available upon request or by following the links provided.

Table 1

COUNTRY	INSTITUTE	RESEARCHER	ACTIVITY	EVIDENCE	NOTES	TARGET GROUP
The Netherlands	UU		Open Forum Event, Utrecht 18 September 2013, 20.00-22.30 Announcement: http://www.uu.nl/faculty/leg/NL/Actueel/agenda/Pages/Open-Forum-Discussie-Project-bEUcitizen.aspx	http://beucitizen.eu/news/eu-citizenship-many-pieces-but-what-should-the-puzzle-look-like/	Open forum discussion organised in light of the project's Kick-Off meeting in Utrecht	General public, Policy makers and Academic Community
		Hanneke van Eijken	De Europese Unie & Europese burgers	PPT presentation	lecture given on European citizenship. Use of the logo in the presentation.	children between 8-11 years old
		Hanneke van Eijken	DAMR Autumn meeting, 20 September 2013, Utrecht University	DAMR Programme	Conference organized for the Dutch Association for Migration Research, in which researcher of bEUcitizen were invited to speak about the first results of their research	Academic Community

⁴ To prevent activities to be listed more than once, all activities sorted by country and institute rather than target group, while a number of dissemination activities were targeted at more than one group.

Table 1 continued

The Netherlands	UU	Hanneke van Eijken	Editorial for the European Gender Equality Law Review : ' <i>European Citizenship, Gender Equality and Fundamental Rights: Different Paths or Coming to a Crossroads?</i> '	http://ec.europa.eu/justice/gender-equality/files/law_reviews/egelr_2013_2_final_web_en.pdf	Reference to the project in the biography of the author	Academic Community, Policy makers, experts
		Sybe de Vries	Presentatie seminar Toetreding EU tot het EVRM (samen met Dr. A. Buyse (Universiteit Utrecht), Mr. M. Fierstra (Hoge Raad) en Mr. R. Böcker (Min. BuZa), Utrecht, 25 juni 2013		acknowledgment bEUcitizen	
		Sybe de Vries	Keynote seminar DAMR Autumn Meeting, All Rights Reserved? Barriers Towards European Citizenship (BEUCITIZEN), 20 September 2013	DAMR Programme	Conference organized for the Dutch Association for Migration Research, in which researcher of BEUcitizen were invited to speak about the first results of their research	Academic Community
		Sybe de Vries	Lecture 'Reconciling conflicting economic freedoms with fundamental rights', Stockholm, 29 November 2013 (Kommerskollegium)		acknowledgment bEUcitizen	Academic Community
		Sybe de Vries	Organization and presentation: Kick-Off meeting of the bEUcitizen project with 26 universities and institutions (18-20 September 2013, Utrecht)	Report; www.beucitizen.eu ; PPT presentation	First event organised by the bEUcitizen project, including Open Forum Event where people outside of the project were invited	General public, Policy makers and Academic Community
		Sybe de Vries	Presentation: 'The Consumer Image in Free Movement Law', Congress, Oxford, 27-28 March 2014		Conference organized to discuss the concepts of <i>consumer welfare</i> , <i>consumer protection</i> and <i>consumer interest</i> in different contexts of EU law: legislation, free movement and competition. The bEUcitizen research project was mentioned and acknowledged	Academic Community, Legal scholars

Table 1 continued

		Sybe de Vries	Organization and presentation of the congress 'Five years Legally binding EU Charter', in collaboration with the Institute of European and Comparative Law, University of Oxford, May 9, 2014	Programme	Conference on the state of play in the protection of fundamental rights in the EU.	
The Netherlands	UU	Maarten Prak	<i>Access to the Trade: Urban Craft Guilds and Social and Geographical Mobility in Early Modern Europe</i> , , ESSHC Vienna, April 2014, Thursday 24 April 2014 14.00 - 16.00, Y-7 - SOC11 : Institutions of Exclusion? Guilds, Citizenship and Inequality in Early Modern Europe	https://esshc.socialhistory.org/esshc-user/program?network=0&extsearch=Prak presentation PDF	The team working in WP3 has organised a session at the European Social Science History Congress in Vienna, in April 2014. Three of the four papers in the session were delivered by team members. In the core presentation, a first draft of the first deliverable, the project and its logo were explicitly mentioned, as shown in the accompanying slides.	Academic Community (Historian and social scientists)
Croatia	UNIZG	Viktor Koska	<i>Refugees, displaced person and citizens: the case of Croatian Serbs'</i> , University of Liverpool Europe and the World Centre. Yugoslavia Then and Now. Speakers: Viktor Kostka (University of Zagreb, Croatia) and Gezim Krasniqi (University of Edinburgh). - a Seminar event. 12th March 2014	PPT presentation	bEUcitizen was directly promoted during the presentation, also through the use of the official logo	Academic Community, students, UOL staff, anyone interested in the topic
		Viktor Koska	Refugees, displaced person and citizens: the case of Croatian Serbs', The Challenges of Europe: The Quest for Citizenship (Inclusion and Exclusion in Contemporary European Societies) Dubrovnik, 7-11 April 2014	PPT presentation	bEUcitizen was directly promoted during the presentation, also through the use of the official logo	Masters and PhD students
Denmark	AAU	Lise Rolandsen Augustin	The Othering of Domestic Violence: The EU and Cultural Framings of Violence against Women, Social Politics (Winter 2013) 20 (4):534-557.	http://sp.oxfordjournals.org/content/early/2013/10/21/sp.jxt020.full	Reference to the project in the biography of the author	Academic Community
Denmark	UCPH	Ulla Neergaard	President FIDE Congress 2014	http://fide2014.eu/	Many of our researcher were present as discussant and rapporteurs.	Academic Community, Policy makers

Table 1 continued

Germany	GUF	Sandra Seubert	“Representative Government and Political Freedom”, presented at the Internationale Mill-Konferenz, Bucerius Law School Hamburg, 5-6 June 2014	.docx + programme Mill Conference + Ppt slide displayed during the presentation	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the context of our project work	Academic Community
		Sandra Seubert	“Citizenship and Animal Rights”, presented at the Conference of the Political Theory Section of the DVPW (German Political Science Association), University of Hamburg, 12-14 March 2014	.docx + Ppt slide displayed during the presentation	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the context of our project work	Academic Community
		Daniel Gaus	“Demoi-kratie ohne Demos-kratie – welche Polity braucht eine demokratische EU?“, presented at the Political Science Colloquium, University of Mainz, 29 January 2014	.docx Ppt slide displayed during the presentation	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the context of our project work	Academic Community
		Daniel Gaus	“Demoi-cracy without Demos-cracy: What Polity for a Democratic EU?” at the conference “Europe, Democracy and Critical Theory. A German-Italian Workshop on Jürgen Habermas’s Theory”, Forschungskolleg Humanwissenschaften Bad Homburg/Germany, 4-6 December 2013	Programme + Demoi-cracy without demos-cracy – what polity for a democratic EU?.doc	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the context of our project work	Academic Community
		Daniel Gaus	“Beyond the Systems Approach to Deliberative Democracy: Reconstructive Theory and the Epistemic Dimension of Democracy“ at the conference “Epistemic Dimensions of Democracy Revisited: Normative and Empirical Perspectives”, Princeton University, 30 April 2014.	.pdf + Ppt slide displayed during the presentation	The talk was introduced as thought developed in the context of our project work	Academic Community
		Daniel Gaus	Rational Reconstruction as a Method of Political Theory between Social Critique and Empirical Political Science, Constellations Volume 20, Issue 4, pages 553–570, December 2013	http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/1/1467-8675.12064/full	Reference to the project in the biography of the author	Academic Community
Hungary	CEU	Marie-Pierre Granger	20 September 2013 – Keynote speech – Dutch Association for Migration Research, Autumn meeting, Utrecht . Presentation: ‘EU citizens and their civil rights - a blurred picture’.	1. Speech PDF 2. DAMR meeting programme .doc	presentation which introduced the bEUcitizen project, in particular research to be carried out in WP7 and WP5.	Academic community

Table 1 continued

Italy	UNITN	Elena Ioriatti	INTEGRAZIONE E CITTADINANZA EUROPEA NEL CONTESTO DEL PLURILINGUISMO Una conversazione sui rapporti tra lingua e diritto in Europa (6 March 2014)	program PDF	Reference to bEUcitizen project was made, explaining the project itself and the current temporary results of the research	Academic Community
Poland	UJ	Marcin Wujczyk	THE HISTORY AND CURRENT DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL RIGHTS IN POLAND	PDF of part of the issue including article concerning our researches	the outcome of the research and the report for the 6 packages is published in the review Yearbook of Labour Law and Social Policy. The review is one of few national yearbooks focused on labour law and social policy.	The review is read by most of labour law academics as well as practitioners interested in that field
UK	LSE	Patrick Wallis	Open Access? Guilds and Citizenship in Early Modern England, ESSHC Vienna, April 2014, Thursday 24 April 2014 14.00 - 16.00 Y-7 - SOC11 : Institutions of Exclusion? Guilds, Citizenship and Inequality in Early Modern Europe	draft PDF PPT presentation https://esshc.socialhistory.org/esshc-user/program/?network=0&textsearch=wallis	The ESSHC session was a panel organised on the topic of the project.	Academic Community (Historian and social scientists)
UK	UOXF	Elaine Chase, Martin Seeleib-Kaiser	Migration, EU Citizenship, and Social Europe - Essay in Social Europe Journal , 14/01/2014	http://www.social-europe.eu/2014/01/eu-citizenship-social-europe/	Essay published in Social Journal Europe with reference to bEUcitizen	Academic Community
The Netherlands + Croatia	UU + UNIZG	Wieger Bakker, Viktor Koska (as directors) + Frans van Waarden, Brigitte Unger, Marcel Hoogenboom, Trudie Knijn (speakers)	Biannual international (post) graduate course: CHALLENGES OF EUROPE - Edition 9: THE QUEST FOR CITIZENSHIP (7-11 April 2014, Inter University Centre (IUC) Dubrovnik (Croatia))	http://www.inclusionexclusion.eu/the-2014-course	The 2014 edition of the Challenges of Europe course was developed in the context of the bEUcitizen project.	Academic Community

Beyond those activities, the bEUcitizen kick-off event, that took place in Utrecht from 18 to 20 September 2013, was of great importance for the initial circulation of the project itself. The open forum, that ended the first day and that was open for the general public, served as source of inspiration and input for our researchers but above all was the place where questions regarding European citizenship were raised.

During the first day, researchers from many different disciplines, representing our 26 Consortium partners from the European Union and outside, were given the chance to meet each other. During the second and third day of the kick-off, the work package coordinators met with their work package participants and discussed concepts, definitions, issues and planning. The kick-off was concluded by a plenary session, where work packages reported on what had been discussed during the meetings.

5.2 BEUCITIZEN PARTNER WEBPAGES

Apart from the activities mentioned above, almost all our Consortium members have a page on their website dedicated to bEUcitizen. Articles about the beginning of the project and its content have been published on peer-reviewed journals, online magazines, University's reports. (table 2)

Table 2

PARTNER	COUNTRY	INSTITUTE	ACTIVITY	EVIDENCE	NOTES
1	The Netherlands	UU	Utrecht Law Review - Volume 10, Issue 1, January 2014 - EU Citizenship Research Project Awarded € 6.5 Million EU Subsidy	https://www.utrechtlawreview.org/index.php?url/article/view/264	
2	Belgium	UA	Page on Institute's website dedicated to bEUcitizen	http://www.researchportal.be/en/project/all-rights-reserved-barriers-towards-european-citizenship-beucitizen--(UA_29076)/	
4	Czech Republic	MU	page on Institute website dedicated to bEUcitizen	http://www.muni.cz/fss/research/projects/24483	
7	Denmark	UCPH	Page on Institute's website dedicated to bEUcitizen	http://jura.ku.dk/english/news/2013/union-citizenship/beucitizen-project/	
12	Hungary	CEU	Page on Institute's website dedicated to bEUcitizen	https://ceur.ceu.hu/node/38332	
14	Israel	HUJI	Link to first bEUcitizen newsletter	http://www.sw.huji.ac.il/en/article/2633	
15	Italy	UNITN	Faculty page dedicated to bEUcitizen	http://web.unitn.it/giuriprudenza/34621/beucitizen	

Table 2 continued

15	Italy	UNITN	RIMUOVERE GLI OSTACOLI PER ESERCITARE LA CITTADINANZA EUROPEA Il progetto BEUCITIZEN dell'UE sui fattori che limitano l'esercizio dei diritti	http://webmagazine.unitn.it/ricerca/1093/rimuovere-gli-ostacoli-per-esercitare-la-cittadinanza-europea	Article on bEUcitizen project, published by Trento University magazine
16	Italy	UNITO	bEUcitizen is mentioned in the website of the project campuscittadinanze.eu	http://campuscittadinanze.eu/2014/02/ http://campuscittadinanze.eu/siti-amici/	
			Page on Institute's website dedicated to bEUcitizen	http://www.unito.it/unitoWAR/page/dipartimenti8/D072/D072_progetti2?path=/BEA%20Repository/5060054	
17	Poland	UJ	Information about the project was included in the report prepared by Jagiellonian University	report PDF	The report includes information about all international projects with participation of academics from our university. The report was sent to all Faculties at Jagiellonian University as well as to some external institution
18	Spain	UNIOVI	Article presenting bEUcitizen published in REUNO - Revista Mensual de Noticias	http://www.uniovei.info/2013/06/la-universidad-de-oviedo-participa-en.html	
19	Spain	UPF	article about the project on University's website	http://www.upf.edu/enoticias/1213/0629.html#.VBubvmSzVU	
20	Spain	IBEI	Page on Institute's website dedicated to bEUcitizen	http://www.ibeio.org/index.php?option=com_content&task=view&id=521&Itemid=120	
25	UK	UOXF	Page on Institute's website dedicated to EUcitizen	http://www.spi.ox.ac.uk/research/details/beucitizen-all-rights-reserved-barrier.html	

5.3 BEUCITIZEN ON THE WORLD WIDE WEB

The project can be found by internet users on the following websites when they use the search term 'bEUcitizen':

- Miesart, Portfolio: <http://www.miesart.com/portfolio/universiteit-van-utrecht/>; this is the website of the Company chosen to develop our website and designing our logo. The page presents bEUcitizen and has a link to its website.
- Emmy van Thiel, <http://www.emmyvanthiel.nl/>; this is the website of the Company that, together with Miesart, developed our printed materials. The page describes in details bEUcitizen's logo and the meaning of the three different colours, corresponding to its three clusters.
- Europa-nu.nl is a site that aims to enable citizens to assess how the EU affects our lives and how we can participate in the decision making process. This site shows the pros and cons of European initiatives from different point of views: the European Union itself, the Dutch government and the interest groups. The website has a page dedicated to events of interest for its public. It is in this section that the Open Forum held during the kick-off event of the project was advertised (http://www.europa-nu.nl/id/vjcf4twov3d8/agenda/open_forum_discussie_project_beucitizen?ctx=vh6ukzb3nnt0&s0e=vifdl6zl7txx)
- LIVEWHAT, project financed by the 7FP that focusses on citizens' resilience in times of economic crises, has a link to our project: http://www.livewhat.unige.ch/?page_id=39

5.4 BEUCITIZEN NEWSLETTER

The first newsletter of the bEUcitizen research project was sent around in December 2013. Newsletters are sent out approximately every 6 months, in July and December.

Find the first newsletter [here](#)

The second newsletter can be found [here](#).

ANNEX

FIGURE 1 WEBSITE HOMEPAGE

BEUCITIZEN
BARRIERS TOWARDS EU CITIZENSHIP

This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no 520294.

Home Our project Our people Blog Publications Agenda News search our website Search

Barriers to European Citizenship

Welcome to the webpage of the bEUcitizen research project. Our research focusses on the barriers that still exist to realize and exercise citizenship rights of EU citizens. This project aims to include all aspects of citizenship:

- How did it develop historically? How did people gain citizenship rights (and economic rights and in which order)?
- What about social, economic, political rights? Are there still barriers to these rights and do they sometimes clash? For example with the rights for different categories of citizens?
- Do gender and generational differences play a role in realizing and exercising rights as EU citizens?
- Are there different rights, different levels of realization and exercising for minorities? How is this affected by migration?

[see all](#)

Blog

26.11.2014, Comparison of United Nations and European Union Economic rights [read](#)
Economic rights are considered human rights and, as such, they are...
Author Carmen BENAVIDES GONZÁLES

19.11.2014, Promoting Children as Active Citizens: the Role of Legal Clinics [read](#)
Children are among the people who encounter most barriers to the...
Author Joelle LONG

[see all blog items](#)

Publications

Policy Essay: Semi-Sovereign Welfare States, Social Rights of EU Migrant Citizens and the Need for Strong State Capacities [read](#)
Research Essay published on 1 December 2014 in the online Social...

A Report on the transposition of EU guidelines and directives in the most recent 27 National Reform Programmes [read](#)
The central aim of this deliverable is to identify possible trends EU...

[see all publications](#)

News

01.12.2014, The EU Charter of Fundamental Rights – five years later [read](#)
Today the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights turns 5 years old. The...

19.11.2014, Consumers rights - CJEU Judgment in Schultz case (C-369/11) [read](#)
In the judgment in joined cases C-369/11 and C-400/11

[see all news items](#)

Agenda

06.12.2014, The EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the Week... [read](#)

11.12.2014, Seminar – Citizenship & the EU Charter: [read](#)

04.02.2016, 3rd "Equal is not Enough" Conference &... [read](#)

06.02.2016, TRAINING SEMINAR ON THE EU CHARTER OF FUNDAMENTAL [read](#)

29.06.2016, bEUcitizen conference 2016 [read](#)

[see all agenda items](#)

Twitter Feed

@bEUcitizen RT @EU_News1: Germany revealed as main destination of EU migrants, as Poland vows to veto UK <http://t.co/oOUyOya9XA>

@bEUcitizen Essay on #SocialRights of #EU #Migrant #citizens written by Martin Geelkebe-Kaiser and Elaine Chace @SocialEurope <http://t.co/ia0ekh0vRu>

@bEUcitizen RT @SocialEurope: New essay on social rights of EU migrant citizens in cooperation with Oxford University and PES London <http://t.co/SIJRhe...>

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FIGURE 2 GOOGLE ANALYTICS

FIGURE 3 SOCIAL NETWORKS (TWITTER & FACEBOOK)

FIGURE 4 FACEBOOK OVERVIEW

